

SITE GPR	YEAR 10	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.6788 Max: 62.83	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1206 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		University of Michigan Kelsey Museum of Archaeology Gabii Project
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 721-723	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 159	
DEFINITION Bigger stones below 1181					Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1181	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are						SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic			Geological		Organic		
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
						Compaction	
						Color	
						<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
						<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit				Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Southern Limit							
<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Western Limit							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Eastern Limit							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1181				Covers: 1223			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS Stones left in situ							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: south central Area B, near southern edge of excavation, Room 1. Shape: Irregular							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: *Roughly E-W, but curves*

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: *—*

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type *—*

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Irregular basalt + tufo stones set within a cut in the bedrock. Appears to curve, roughly aligned with trench cut in bedrock (SU1235).

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

These irregular stones appear to represent a feature of some sort, probably a curving rubble-built wall aligned with the semicircular cut in the bedrock. It was mostly dismantled prior to the leveling of the area for construction of the surrounding building. One stone appears to continue underneath the steps of the southern wall (1184). Further excavation outside room 1, to the north + east, would help clarify these features.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *S. FARR*

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Revised by *CPM*

on *26.7.2010*

PDFd by *JSM*

on *26/7/2010*

Entered by

on